

THE INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SLEEP DISTURBANCES AND HEADACHE INTENSITY IN MIGRAINE

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Abstract. *Migraine is a common neurological disorder characterized by recurrent headaches, often accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and sensitivity to light and sound. Sleep disorders, including insomnia, obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), and restless leg syndrome, have been frequently reported in migraine patients. The interconnection between these two conditions suggests a bidirectional influence where poor sleep can trigger migraines, while migraines can further disrupt sleep. The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide valuable insights into the shared pathophysiology between migraine and sleep disorders, as well as to offer a targeted approach to treatment. Analyzing how sleep disturbances contribute to migraine progression can help healthcare professionals tailor more effective interventions. Additionally, understanding the role of neurochemical changes, such as fluctuations in serotonin and melatonin levels, could lead to improved pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment options.*

Keywords: *migraine, sleep disorders, comorbidity, sleep quality, headache, insomnia, sleep apnea, neurological disorders, circadian rhythm, serotonin, cognitive behavioral therapy.*

Introduction. Sleep disorders and headaches—especially migraines—are classified among chronic conditions. Studies indicate that the prevalence of insomnia among patients with migraines ranges from 25% to 70%. Research has shown that approximately 15% of the population has experienced migraine attacks, with 44% of them reporting insufficient sleep duration (<8 hours), and 30% experiencing prolonged sleep onset latency (>35 minutes) (Song TJ, Yun CH, Cho SJ, Kim WJ, Yang KI, Chu MK, 2019; C. Tiseo, 2020).

Modern neuroimaging techniques and laboratory biomarkers provide evidence for a shared pathophysiological basis. The brain's anatomical architecture—particularly the diencephalon and brainstem—includes central structures responsible for regulating sleep-wake cycles. These centers operate under the influence of neurotransmitters involved in migraine pathogenesis (S. Duan, 2022).

Several theories have been proposed to explain the connection between migraines and sleep disorders. One such theory involves circadian rhythm disruption. Migraine attacks often occur in the early morning or at night, indicating a close association with sleep cycles. A higher frequency of REM (rapid eye movement) sleep can lead to awakenings accompanied by headaches. Conversely, migraine attacks themselves hinder restful sleep, particularly during deep sleep phases. Authors Simpson N.S., Scott-Sutherland J., Gautam S., Setna N., and Haack M. (2018) have demonstrated these phenomena at the level of functional bioelectrical activity (N.V. Vashenko et al., 2021).

Another theory implicates hypothalamic dysfunction, highlighting a bidirectional relationship between migraines and insomnia. Among sleep disturbances, one of the most

significant contributors is sleep-related breathing disorders, such as apnea. Oxygen deficiency during sleep can provoke brief arousals, and this is particularly common in overweight individuals.

Recent studies have also identified restless legs syndrome (RLS) as one of the migraine-associated syndromes. Occurring in about 28% of patients, RLS is notably more prevalent among those with primary headaches and migraines compared to those without. Evidence suggests that RLS is linked to dysfunction in the dopaminergic system and appears more frequently in patients suffering from migraines. Dopamine is one of the key neurotransmitters implicated in migraine pathogenesis. Consequently, many migraine patients report poor sleep quality (F.S. Saidvaliev et al., 2023).

The comorbid nature of migraines and sleep disorders complicates diagnosis, worsens patient quality of life, and necessitates an integrative clinical approach (E.M. Yevdokimova et al., 2019; Y.G. Karnaux et al., 2020). Evaluating and managing sleep disturbances in patients with migraines is essential, as improving sleep quality can significantly reduce both the frequency and severity of headache episodes.

Research Objective: To study the relationship between sleep disorders and the risk of migraine development based on age and gender factors

Materials and methods. The material for this study consisted of patients experiencing sleep disturbances, particularly those with difficulty falling asleep, frequent nocturnal awakenings, and shallow sleep. In addition, these patients reported headaches consistent with the clinical features of migraine. The research was conducted during 2024–2025 at the Department of Neurology, Multidisciplinary Clinic of Samarkand State Medical University (SamSMU), as well as at the private clinic “Inova.”

The main group comprised 58 patients diagnosed with migraine, while the control group consisted of 41 healthy volunteers undergoing preventive examinations at the outpatient clinic of SamSMU. The diagnosis was established based on the International Classification of Headache Disorders, 3rd edition (ICHD-III). Among the migraine patients, 9 individuals presented with migraine with aura. The main group included 53 women and 5 men, with a mean age of 35.5 ± 10 years. The control group included 30 women and 11 men, with a mean age of 36 ± 9.2 years.

A comparison group included 37 individuals (31 women and 6 men) who showed signs of migraine but did not report any sleep disturbances. There were no statistically significant differences in age or sex between the groups, and baseline comparability was ensured.

In the first stage, patients completed a detailed questionnaire (developed and approved at the 7th departmental meeting in 2024). In addition to standard clinical information (complaints, migraine duration, disease history, etc.), the questionnaire assessed the presence of unhealthy habits (such as smoking and alcohol consumption), comorbid conditions (including arterial hypertension, diabetes), body weight status (patients with obesity were excluded), and emotional state indicators (anxiety and depressive symptoms).

At the second stage, after group classification, patients were tested using a range of instruments to assess the interrelation between migraine and sleep disturbances. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), a self-administered questionnaire with 19 items, was used to evaluate sleep quality. It assesses factors such as subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, use of sleep medication, and daytime dysfunction. A PSQI score >5 indicates poor sleep quality, with a diagnostic sensitivity of 98.7% and specificity of 84.4%.

The Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (SAS) and Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS) each consist of 20 items and measure anxiety and depression on a scale from 20 to 80. Scores between 25 and 100 indicate a moderate level, while scores above 100 suggest a high level of psychological distress. A threshold score of 50 is considered indicative of clinically significant anxiety or depression.

The Visual Analog Scale (VAS) was used to assess subjective pain intensity. The Migraine Disability Assessment Scale (MIDAS), comprising 5 items, categorizes work-related disability as follows: scores from 6–10 indicate mild disability, 11–20 moderate disability, and scores above 20 indicate severe disability. The Migraine-Specific Quality of Life (MSQ) scale was also used, where higher scores reflect better quality of life.

Statistical analysis was performed using standard data sets on a personal computer, applying the Mann–Whitney U-test for group comparisons. A significance level of $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically reliable.

Results. In accordance with the study objectives, patients completed questionnaires assessing, first and foremost, levels of anxiety and depression. The results showed that PSQI (sleep quality), SAS (anxiety), and SDS (depression) scores were significantly higher in the main group compared to the control group ($P < 0.05$).

Analysis of the relationship between sleep patterns and the risk of migraine development revealed a notable association between poor sleep quality and increased migraine frequency. Overall, the odds ratio was calculated as 1.7, indicating that sleep disturbances substantially increase the frequency of migraine attacks.

When patients were further divided into subgroups based on age, gender, unhealthy habits (e.g., smoking), blood pressure levels, and body weight, the correlation between these variables and sleep quality in migraine patients yielded an odds ratio of 1.69. This means the risk of developing migraine increased proportionally with the intensity of each of the contributing factors.

The highest correlation was observed in women over the age of 36 ($P < 0.05$).

When comparing the PSQI index in the main group (migraine with sleep disturbance) and the comparison group (migraine without sleep disturbance), the risk of migraine was found to be significantly higher in patients with impaired sleep quality. The PSQI score in the main group ranged from 5.9 to 6.4 points.

Further analysis of individual PSQI components—such as sleep latency, sleep duration, sleep efficiency (depth), subjective sleep quality, sleep disturbances (frequency of awakenings, difficulty falling or staying asleep), daytime sleepiness, and use of sleep medication—showed that each of these factors contributed to the prognosis of migraine. In the most severe cases, each indicator independently showed statistical significance with $P < 1.0$.

Figure 1. Analysis indicators of the relationship between migraine and sleep disturbances in the control group

Table 1. Predictive indicators of the association between sleep disturbances and migraine based on study data

No	Indicators	AG	Sensitivity, %	Specific%	P
1	Sleep quality index (PSQI)	0,88	56	95	<0,001
2	Subjective perception of sleep disturbance	0,77	50	81	<0,001
3	Sleep cycle	0,54	31	88	<0,05
4	Clinical disturbances of sleep disorders	0,78	95	35	<0,001
5	Ineffective sleep perception	0,60	40	89	<0,001
6	Daytime sleepiness	0,50	19,7	92	<0,001
7	Use of sleep-inducing medications	0,49	9	97	<0,001
8	Anxiety	0,8	63	79	<0,001
9	Depression	0,59	42	77	<0,001

Furthermore, it was found that among patients with higher levels of depression, the PSQI scores predicting migraine risk were significantly higher compared to those with elevated anxiety levels. The next stage of the study involved comparing data on pain intensity assessed via the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) with indicators such as sleep disturbances, migraine-related

disability measured by the MIDAS scale, migraine-specific quality of life (MSQ), and anxiety and depression levels evaluated using the SAS and SDS scales. Correlation analysis demonstrated a direct association between poor sleep quality, increased pain intensity, decreased quality of life, and higher levels of anxiety and depression. Additionally, in subgroups of patients stratified by age, gender, blood pressure, high body weight, and presence of harmful habits, poor sleep quality was consistently linked to more severe pain syndrome and elevated levels of psychological distress.

Table 2: Comparative Indicators Between the Size Index and Sleep Disorder Criteria

№	Indicators	AG	Control group	P
1	Sleep Quality Index PSQI	5,9-6,4 ball	2,5-3 ball	<0,05
2	VAS scale	7,5±2,3	3±1	<0,05
3	MIDAS scale	24±5	5±1	<0,05
4	MSQ scale	35±2	60±10	<0,05
5	SAS / anxiety	45,7±9	20±10	<0,05
6	SDS / depression	46±13	19±11	<0,05

Conclusion. Thus, the results of the study support the hypothesis that the components of sleep disturbances—including sleep quality, sleep efficiency, and individual sleep characteristics—are closely associated with the severity of migraine-related pain syndrome. Moreover, the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was shown to reflect several clinical features and prognostic factors of migraine-related sleep disorders. Among subgroups divided by age, high body weight, harmful habits, gender differences, and elevated blood pressure, the association between migraine and sleep quality was particularly pronounced in patients with migraine with aura. However, due to the small number of male participants, gender-based conclusions require cautious interpretation. Statistically, sleep disturbances significantly increase the risk of developing migraine without aura, and the use of the PSQI provides an effective tool for identifying early stages of sleep disorders. This, in turn, allows for timely optimization of treatment in migraine patients by improving sleep quality and efficiency.

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